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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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EQUAL VOICE IN THE CLASSROOM: A GENDER-BASED APPROACH

UDK: 378.147.227

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Abstract: This study investigates gender-based classroom participation among bachelor's degree students at Fergana State University through an online survey. The findings reveal a perceived male-dominated discourse and gender-based hesitation in classroom interaction, alongside strong student support for gender-neutral instructional strategies. The results support existing research advocating structured and inclusive pedagogical practices aimed at ensuring equal voice and participation in the classroom.

Key words: gender equality, classroom participation, patriarchal norms, gender-neutral education, student engagement, inclusive pedagogy.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot Farg'ona davlat universiteti bakalavriat talabalari orasida auditoriyadagi genderga oid ishtirok xususiyatlarini onlayn so'rovnoma asosida o'rganadi. Natijalar auditoriya muhokamalarida erkaklar nutqining ustunligi haqidagi tasavvurlar mavjudligini hamda genderga asoslangan ikkilanish holatlari kuzatilishini ko'rsatadi. Shu bilan birga, talabalar orasida genderga neytral ta'lim strategiyalarini qo'llashga nisbatan yuqori darajadagi qo'llab-quvvatlash aniqlangan. Tadqiqot natijalari auditoriyada teng fikr bildirish imkoniyatini ta'minlashga qaratilgan tizimli va inklyuziv pedagogik yondashuvlarni qo'llash zarurligini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: gender tengligi, auditoriyada ishtirok, patriarxal me'yorlar, genderga neytral ta'lim, talabalar faolligi, inklyuziv pedagogika.

Аннотация: Данное исследование анализирует особенности гендерного участия в учебных занятиях среди студентов бакалавриата Ферганского государственного университета на основе онлайн-опроса. Полученные результаты показывают воспринимаемое доминирование мужского дискурса и наличие гендерной неуверенности при участии в обсуждениях, а также демонстрируют значительную поддержку студентами гендерно-нейтральных образовательных стратегий. Результаты подтверждают выводы научной литературы, обосновывающей необходимость внедрения структурированных и инклюзивных педагогических практик для обеспечения равного участия и выражения мнений в учебной аудитории.

Ключевые слова: гендерное равенство, участие в учебном процессе, патриархальные нормы, гендерно-нейтральное образование, вовлечённость студентов, инклюзивная педагогика.

INTRODUCTION

Gender inequality in classrooms remains a global concern, rooted in broader social and cultural norms. Patriarchy, defined as male dominance across political, social, and educational spheres, shapes both expectations and interactions within learning environments (Hazarika et al., 2023, p. 2). Male students are often given more opportunities to lead discussions, while female students are socialized to participate quietly or defer to male authority (Carlsson et al., 2019, p. 4). These dynamics can diminish girls' confidence, limit their academic aspirations, and restrict access to male-dominated fields, particularly STEM (Galano et al., 2023, p. 3).

Historically, school curricula and classroom practices have reinforced gender roles. Men have frequently been portrayed as intellectual leaders, while women are often assigned domestic or supportive roles (Koseoglu et al., 2020, p. 6). Such stereotyping shapes students' self-perception and the expectations of teachers and peers (Xiang et al., 2018, p. 12; Chan et al., 2022, p. 5). Evidence shows that these biases influence both enrollment and achievement, perpetuating unequal participation and long-term disparities between male and female students (Olsson et al., 2018, p. 7).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Patriarchy—defined as the systemic dominance of men in social, political, and educational spheres—continues to influence classroom dynamics by privileging male voices and leadership (Hazarika et al., 2023, p. 2). In schools, this often manifests through informal interactional patterns where boys are encouraged to speak and lead, while girls are expected to remain cooperative and reserved (Carlsson et al., 2019, p. 4). Ossai (2024) links these patterns to deeply rooted historical norms that legitimize masculine authority and restrict female participation in intellectual domains (pp. 50–51). The long-term consequences, including reduced self-esteem and limited access to male-dominated fields such as STEM, are well documented (Galano et al., 2023, p. 3). Together, these studies demonstrate that patriarchal structures operate not only at institutional levels but also within everyday classroom discourse, shaping students' confidence, aspirations, and voice.

Historical curricular practices have reinforced these inequalities by portraying men as intellectual leaders and women in domestic or supportive roles (Koseoglu et al., 2020, p. 6). Xiang et al. (2018, p. 12) argue that such stereotypes influence students' self-perception, while Chan et al. (2022, p. 5) highlight how girls are often discouraged from STEM and boys from caregiving or arts-related professions. Empirical evidence from Olsson et al. (2018, p. 7) confirms that these norms affect both enrollment patterns and academic outcomes. Classroom interaction studies further reveal that teachers may unconsciously call on male students more frequently (Yu, 2023, p. 9; Igurdardottir et al., 2022, p. 8), while female contributions are sometimes overlooked (Khoumich et al., 2020, p. 176). Textbooks and instructional materials also perpetuate biased representations (Guichot-Reina et al., 2023, p. 4; Abdelhay & Benhaddouche, 2015, p. 437). Correlatively, these findings show how structural, curricular, and interactional factors collectively reproduce unequal participation.

Gender-neutral education emerges as a strategic response to these entrenched disparities. Guerrero and Guerrero-Puerta (2023, p. 65) describe it as a framework that ensures equitable opportunities for expression and exploration free from stereotypical constraints. Ossai (2024, pp. 51–52) emphasizes that gender-neutral strategies challenge patriarchal assumptions while fostering creativity, empathy, and critical thinking. Practical interventions—such as rotating leadership roles or randomly selecting speakers—have been shown to balance classroom voice (Shah, 2021, p. 52), while exposure to diverse role models broadens students' career aspirations (Dele-Ajayi et al., 2020, p. 3). Curriculum diversification (Rogers et al., 2019, p. 10), inclusive language use, and bias-aware assessments (Alordiah & Agbajor, 2014, p. 11), combined with anti-bullying and equitable management strategies (Domínguez-Martínez et al., 2019, p. 545; Lewis et al., 2022, p. 13), create structurally supportive environments. These approaches are reinforced through professional development that helps educators recognize and counter unconscious bias (Wang, 2023, p. 6).

Research consistently demonstrates that gender-neutral classrooms enhance both academic performance and student well-being. Students in inclusive environments report higher engagement, stronger self-confidence, and increased participation across traditionally gendered subjects (Merma-Molina et al., 2021, p. 8). Kollmayer et al. (2020, p. 14) further show that removing gender barriers promotes freer self-expression and improved academic results, while Croft et al. (2021, p. 70) link equitable dialogue to greater social cohesion. Although critics argue that gender-neutral education may conflict with cultural traditions (Karlidag-Dennis et al., 2020, p. 625), scholars clarify that its aim is not to erase identity but to expand opportunity (Ossai, 2024, p. 53; Eriksson et al., 2020, p. 5). Evidence-based advocacy highlighting improved achievement and broader career engagement (Shutts et al., 2017, p. 15; Krishna & Orhun, 2020, p. 200) strengthens the case for reform. Particularly in social studies classrooms, integrating gender-neutral strategies fosters critical engagement with historical norms and prepares students to challenge inequitable systems beyond school (Ossai, 2024, pp. 54–55). Collectively, these findings affirm that dismantling patriarchal constraints through gender-neutral education cultivates empowered and inclusive learning spaces where every student's voice is equally valued.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

An online survey was conducted among 24 bachelor's degree students at Fergana State University. The questionnaire included multiple-choice and open-ended questions examining perceptions of gender equality in classroom participation, personal experiences of hesitation, and suggested strategies for promoting equal voice.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The findings reveal a clear perception of unequal classroom voice among the 24 bachelor's degree students at Fergana State University. Regarding Q1, half of the respondents ($n = 12$, 50%) believe that male and female students do not have equal opportunities to speak in class, while only 6 students (25%) perceive participation as equal and another 6 (25%) remain unsure. This indicates that a majority either directly observe inequality or

are uncertain about fairness, suggesting that equal voice is not consistently visible in the classroom environment. The equal distribution between “Yes” and “Not sure” (each 25%) further highlights ambiguity in students’ experiences, possibly reflecting variability across courses or instructors.

Figure 1: Perceived Inequality and Male-Dominated Participation

The responses to Q2 reinforce this perception of imbalance. Overall, 12 students (50%) report that mostly males speak more often in class, while 6 students (25%) perceive participation as equal. Five respondents (20.83%) state that it depends on the subject, and only 1 student (4.17%) believes that mostly females speak more often. Notably, among those who answered “No” to equal opportunities in Q1 (n = 12), 11 students (45.83% of the total) identified mostly males as speaking more frequently, showing a strong alignment between perceived inequality and observed male-dominated discourse. In contrast, those who answered “Yes” (n = 6) were more likely to report equal participation (5 students, 20.83% of the total). These patterns collectively suggest that male-dominated interaction remains a prominent perception within the sample, while equal participation is acknowledged but less frequently experienced, supporting concerns raised in the literature about persistent gendered classroom dynamics.

The responses to Q3 show that gender-based hesitation is present but not universal among the 24 respondents. Six students (25%) reported that they have felt hesitant to speak because of their gender, while the largest group—11 students (45.83%)—stated that they have not experienced such hesitation. Meanwhile, 7 students (29.17%) selected “Sometimes,” indicating situational or context-dependent discomfort. Although nearly half deny personal hesitation, the combined proportion of those answering “Yes” or “Sometimes” (13 students, 54.17%) suggests that more than half of the sample has at least occasionally experienced gender-related barriers to participation. This highlights that even when inequality is not constant, it remains a meaningful factor influencing classroom voice.

Figure 2: Gender-Based Hesitation and Preferred Inclusion Strategies

Regarding Q4, preferences for improving equal voice are relatively evenly distributed, indicating no single dominant solution. Four strategies—Random selection, Rotating leadership, Small group work, and Teacher training—each received 5 responses (20.83%). Anonymous digital tools followed closely with 4 responses (16.67%). Among students who answered “Yes” to Q3 ($n = 6$), support was strongest for Random selection and Teacher training (2 students each, 8.33%, respectively), suggesting that those who experience hesitation favor structured or instructor-led interventions. Students who answered “No” ($n = 11$) most frequently preferred Small group work (3 students, 12.5%) and Random selection (3 students, 12.5%), reflecting a focus on participatory formats. Those selecting “Sometimes” ($n = 7$) were more inclined toward Rotating leadership and Anonymous digital tools (2 students each, 8.33%). Overall, the data indicate both recognition of gender-related participation barriers and broad support for diversified, structural strategies to foster more inclusive classroom dialogue.

The open-ended responses to Q5 reveal a nuanced but recurring perception that gender influences classroom participation through interactional patterns, teacher behavior, cultural expectations, and subject-specific differences. Several students explicitly describe male-dominated discourse, noting that boys interrupt more often, speak louder in debates, volunteer faster, and are frequently assigned leadership roles by default. Others highlight teacher-related factors, such as educators responding faster to boys, overlooking girls’ raised hands, or unconsciously preferring confident male students, as well as failing to notice subtle exclusion. Cultural norms are also identified as shaping participation, with girls described as more reserved, afraid of negative peer comments, or hesitant in large groups. Subject variation emerges as an important theme: boys are seen as dominating STEM classes, while girls participate more actively in humanities and language courses. At the same time, a minority of responses emphasize equality or alternative explanations, stating that participation depends more on personality than gender, that online formats feel safer, or that class culture in some cases promotes fairness. Overall, while not universally negative, the majority of comments reflect structural and interactional patterns that privilege more outspoken—often male—students.

The suggestions in Q6 closely correspond to the identified challenges and demonstrate strong support for structured, inclusive reforms. Proposed changes include institutional strategies such as bias-awareness workshops, gender-sensitivity seminars, and clear inclusion policies, alongside practical classroom techniques like tracking participation, structured turn-taking, random selection of speakers, alternating leadership roles, and time limits per speaker. Many respondents advocate pedagogical adjustments, including small-group discussions, mixed-gender teams, collaborative rather than competitive tasks, and providing reflection time before answering. Digital solutions—anonymous Q&A tools, discussion forums, and instant polling applications—are also seen as mechanisms that equalize voice and reduce fear of judgment. Additionally, students stress the importance of cultivating a respectful listening culture and supportive peer feedback. Collectively, these responses indicate both awareness of gender-influenced participation patterns and a clear preference for multi-level interventions—structural, pedagogical, and technological—to create a more balanced and inclusive classroom environment.

The results largely support the theoretical assumptions outlined in the literature review. The finding that 50% of respondents perceive unequal speaking opportunities and that 50% report that mostly male students speak more often aligns with the argument that patriarchal norms continue to shape classroom discourse (Hazarika et al., 2023; Ossai, 2024). Students’ observations that boys interrupt more frequently, volunteer faster, and are often assigned leadership roles reflect the interactional patterns described by Carlsson (2019) and Yu (2023), who emphasize how informal classroom dynamics privilege male assertiveness. The data therefore confirm that gendered participation is not merely theoretical but perceptible within the Uzbek higher education context.

The subject-specific variation reported by students—male dominance in STEM and stronger female participation in humanities—corroborates Chan’s (2022) and Galano et al.’s (2023) findings on gendered academic identity and discipline-based stereotypes. Such differentiation suggests that inequality is not uniform but mediated by disciplinary culture. At the same time, the fact that 25% perceive equal opportunities and 25% remain unsure indicates partial progress or variability depending on instructors, which resonates with Wang’s (2023) emphasis on the role of teacher awareness in shaping inclusive environments.

Importantly, more than half of respondents (54.17%) reported feeling hesitant to speak because of gender either consistently or sometimes. This supports research linking classroom voice to self-confidence, stereotype internalization, and fear of judgment (Kollmayer et al., 2020; Croft et al., 2021). Students’ references to teachers overlooking girls’ raised hands or unconsciously preferring confident male students parallel findings by Igurardottir et al. (2022) and Khoumich et al. (2020), who highlight subtle yet persistent instructional bias. Thus, the empirical data reinforce the claim that structural and interactional inequalities coexist.

The proposed solutions strongly align with gender-neutral strategies discussed in the literature. Students’ preference for random selection, rotating leadership, structured turn-taking, teacher training, and digital tools directly reflects interventions identified by Shah (2021), Guerrero and Guerrero-Puerta (2023), and Ossai

(2024). The emphasis on bias-awareness workshops and participation tracking supports Wang's (2023) assertion that professional development is central to dismantling unconscious bias. Therefore, the results not only confirm existing research but also demonstrate that students themselves recognize and advocate for evidence-based reforms.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study demonstrates that perceptions of unequal classroom voice persist among bachelor's degree students at Fergana State University. While some respondents experience fairness, a significant proportion observe male-dominated participation patterns and report gender-related hesitation. These findings suggest that patriarchal interaction norms continue to influence classroom discourse, even within contemporary higher education settings.

At the same time, the diversity of responses indicates that inequality is not absolute but context-dependent, varying across subjects and teaching styles. The presence of inclusive practices in some classrooms shows that change is possible when instructors consciously structure participation and promote respectful dialogue. Ultimately, the findings confirm that gender-neutral educational strategies are both necessary and supported by students. By implementing structured participation methods, enhancing teacher awareness, and integrating inclusive pedagogical tools, universities can cultivate equitable learning environments where every student's voice is valued equally.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.